

Background

Background: concisely explain the research area including references, and, where appropriate, relevant policy and practice developments or professional agendas

FoodSEqual Project 'Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities'

The FoodSEqual project is part of a five year national consortium project led by the University of Reading (Prof Carol Wagstaff) and involves academics from Sussex, Kent and Cranfield Universities. It is funded (£6million) by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF) and runs from 1.2.21 until 31.1.26. The Plymouth work-package has already had ethics approved for phase one of the work (PEOS ethics no 2933). This ethics application is focussing on a discrete element of FoodSEqual Plymouth, being carried out in collaboration with a local secondary school.

Project summary

The vision of the FoodSEqual project is to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse disadvantaged communities with choice and agency over the food they consume by co-developing new products, new supply chains and new policy frameworks that deliver affordable, attractive, healthy and sustainable diet. The recent COVID19 global pandemic has illustrated the fragility of the current UK food system. The failure of supply chains to operate, restrictions on social movement and reduction of employment opportunities was felt most extremely by disadvantaged communities. The number of adults who are food insecure in the Britain is estimated to have quadrupled under the COVID-19 lockdown (Loopstra 2020). Drawing together best practice from food system co-production methodologies, the FoodSEqual project will develop a community-informed approach to transform the food system to a model that benefits the environment, provides opportunities for small and large food businesses and gives access to culturally appropriate food for disadvantaged communities.

Plymouth (and school) context

Plymouth has pockets of serious social and economic deprivation, some of which are considered amongst the highest in England in terms of deprivation index (PCC, 2019a), with up to 10 years life expectancy difference between neighbourhoods. Of particular note, are increasing numbers of young people identified at risk of 'food insecurity' (Allerton et al

2019) and high levels of child poverty (18.6% of Plymouth children) (PCC, 2019b). The FoodSEqual Plymouth project is already working closely with the Four Greens Community Trust as our main place based geographical community, in particular Whitleigh, which is ranked 5th in the local index of multiple deprivation (IMD 2019).

Schools play a crucial role in improving children's wellbeing and are an obvious setting for population-level public health nutrition interventions (Woodside et al, 2020). Furthermore, promoting the (human and planetary) health of the school food system can be seen as an essential activity that supports the goals of education. Building food (and nutrition) literacy at a young age is important for skill retention, confidence in food practices and supporting lifelong healthy (and sustainable) eating habits (Carroll et al 2021). This aligns with strategic current government policy drivers to ameliorate the school food culture, tackle childhood obesity and mitigate climate change (Dimbleby, 2021) and informs the context of the current ethics application.

Aims and objectives

Aims and objectives: State what your study will achieve, key findings and any hypotheses. Include how you anticipate the fulfillment of the aims and key questions will move forward knowledge and where appropriate, policy or practice

Aim of the Plymouth FoodSEqual Curriculum enrichment research project:

The aim of this discrete element of FoodSEqual Plymouth is to run a pilot interactive series of food (system) themed events and research activities running up to and during enrichment week (w/b 4th July 2022) for yr 7 and 8 pupils (n=15) [and their families] of Sir John Hunt community college (Whitleigh, Plymouth). [Then if successful, continue into future years to form a longitudinal food and curriculum enrichment project].

Objectives (research activities in bold)

- To set up a working community project/research group for planning and organisation of activities in close collaboration with the school (principal and food teachers)
- To plan and organise four taster sessions (leading up to enrichment week) (Please see Appendix A for planned activities) for pupils to attend to empower/engage them to co-create ideas for enrichment week
- To liaise with relevant local food partners and stakeholders to support the taster day and enrichment week activities

- To support and deliver five days of food themed activities during enrichment week (Appendix A) for pupils of Sir John Hunt school (culminating in final day being 'Food Festival' event)
- **To plan and carry out FoodSEqual research activities so that data collection can take place in alignment with the planned enrichment activities**

This ethics application is pertinent to the SCHOOL arm of FoodSEqual which will run in the first instance 2 March – 10 July 2022 (and possibly also two subsequent years thereafter if this pilot phase is deemed successful). Please see Appendix A for planned activities

Methods

Methods: explain how participants will be recruited (where, by whom, how many; inclusion and exclusion criteria), what data will be collected, how it will be analysed (statistical tests, sample size considerations). This should include references of the particular methodology being used; how it will be employed in relation to this study; which techniques of analysis will be used once data are collected and how this will be applied to the particular data set.

The complex nature of decisions about food is a challenge in young people and children, most often influenced by parents and peers. It is well known that children respond best to interactive and engaging educational approaches and such food literacy educational opportunities are becoming more common (Amin et al 2018). Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodologies are the main methodological focus of FoodSEqual and are well documented for improving the situations of vulnerable people (Crane and O-Regan, 2010). Such empowerment driven person- and community-centred approaches are known to improve wellbeing (Wood et al 2016) and engagement. For this school aspect of the project, the focus will be on methodological approaches that fit with PAR philosophies as well as being tailored to the needs of children.

DESIGN

A pilot public health nutrition intervention (as part of FoodSEqual research project), involving a series of food curriculum enrichment activities aiming to assess **change(?)** in food (system) literacy and school food culture in secondary school pupils (and their teachers). If the pilot is successful, this will run for two subsequent years using similar methodology to create a 3-year longitudinal intervention.

RECRUITMENT

Our pilot place based community of interest for FoodSEqual is the Four Greens Community Trust (north Plymouth) and Whitleigh specifically. We have, to date, been building strong relationships with many key community leaders in the local area. Of particular note, is verbal agreement by the principal teacher that Sir John Hunt Community College will act as 'gatekeeper' to access school pupils and their parents for the purposes of data collection.

The school has already provided verbal agreement, and permissions will be gained officially via a gatekeeper information sheet (Appendix B) and consent form (Appendix C) once ethics is approved. Thereafter the school will provide support to reach pupils (and their parents when relevant) via their already established permissions communication channels (adhering to safeguarding and GDPR policies within the school).

Convenience sampling will be used to access pupils (Namageyo-Funa et al, 2014). The school food technology teachers will identify n=15 pupils (years 7 and 8) to engage in the curriculum enrichment project, therefore we will not be operating an inclusion/exclusion criteria per se. These pupils will be the key participants engaged in the curriculum enrichment project and its research elements. We acknowledge the potential bias this will create for the sample.

PAR Methodological approaches

The Plymouth PI already has a strong track record of delivering successful PAR methods using photo elicitation (Pettinger et al 2017) and other creative methods and is very sensitive to the needs of ethics, emotion and power dynamics of PAR methodologies (Pettinger et al 2018) and is confident to evolve and adapt as necessary the use of creative methods to engage younger audiences, with the support of an already established creative methods toolkit (Plymouth Food Equality Project, 2021).

The focus of this school project will incorporate the broadest holistic socio-cultural role of food in participants' lives and other determining factors influencing childrens' food choices.

Proposed measurement for behaviour and school food culture change

Specific 'mechanisms of action' to measure within behaviour/culture change processes will include:

- 1) Food (system) Literacy - incorporating individual level food and nutrition knowledge; food skills; self-efficacy and confidence; food decisions and ecological factors (Thomas et al 2019) as well as aspirations. These aspects will be measured in children using focus groups (x2) at baseline and endpoint. See appendix D for focus group template

2) School Food Culture – cross-sectional (ie one time point and/or during 3 year period) to observe, assess and map school food culture and environment. Observations and interviews with school teachers (x5)

3) Co-production approaches – where possible the pupils (n=15 participants) themselves will support data collection as part of activities. If we have any very keen pupils we will offer the opportunity to engage further with FoodSEqual project as a ‘community food researchers’ (in alignment with FoodSEqual project parameters – covered by ethical approval in application no. 2833)

These activities will be carried out with a view to mapping onto existing and potential creative food systems tools (e.g. already existing food systems tool <https://www.nourishlife.org/teach/food-system-tools/>) to arrive at an adaptable theory-based toolkit with potential for cross-translation and testing in different school-based contexts across the FoodSEqual project.

Focus groups

Children focus group (x2) at baseline and endpoint. The pupil group (n=15) will be split and each will undertake the focus group during taster day 1 (Wed 2 March) and then again at endpoint (during curriculum enrichment week 7th July). The purpose of the focus groups is to get a sense of food (system) literacy focussing discussions on an established ‘Food literacy framework’ (Thomas et al 2019), and will be informed by tools that have been validated for use with children (Carroll et al 2021). The focus groups will also permit depth of exploration of any perceived improvements in food literacy during the project. Creative approaches will be used to engage the pupils optimally, such as food images, collage, zine, drawing and poetry to support discussions. See Appendix D for focus group template

Parent focus group (x1or2 depending on numbers) on Wed 11 May 2022. Similar topic guide will be used (Appendix D) to gauge parental food literacy levels, with similar engagement approaches being used so that parents are encouraged to discuss their experiences.

Focus groups are an appropriate method of data collection because they enable a focussed group discussion and produce large amounts of concentrated data in a short period of time (Morgan 1998). They are also suitable for children, although developmental considerations are essential for good facilitation (Kennedy et al 2001). We have a highly experienced and fully DBS checked community research consultant (JG) who will be delivering the focus

groups with children and parents. All focus groups will be audio-recorded for transcription purposes.

The facilitators will create a suitable environment that encourages freedom of discussion, aiming to create focus groups where participants are likely to be comfortable with one another. At the start of each focus group, ground-rules will be set and participants will be reminded that a supportive environment can often lead to 'over-disclosure' thus compromising confidentiality. Equally the group dynamics will be managed to ensure all have the opportunity to speak if they wish to and no group member is allowed to dominate the group. It is hoped that all pupils (and their parents) will engage in the focus groups meaning each will be around 6-8 participants (Green and Thorogood, 2014, p130).

Interviews with staff /teachers

These interviews will assess teacher and professional service staff perspectives and school food culture. They will use an adapted Appreciative Inquiry (AI) method. We will recruit up to n=6 teachers from the school (those involved in food, science, cooking related curriculum activities). The AI method presents an alternative to the problem-solving approach underpinning action research and offers an affirmative approach for evaluating and envisioning future initiatives based on optimisation of best practice (Bellinger & Elliot, 2011), emphasising the power of capacity, problem solving and resourcefulness. Questions will be formed in response to the preliminary focus group findings, and will be based around the benefits of food themed curriculum enrichment activities to enable improvement of food literacy in children and parents (See Appendix D for draft schedule).

Observation of school food environment

During our interactions with the various project activities, we will observe, assess and record/map the school food culture and environment. This will be informed by the Food for Life 'Six Steps to transform food culture' document (Soil Association, 2006) and is likely to include observation of food/tech class, to enable us to monitor the interactions between pupils and between pupils and teacher. The purpose of this will be to understand how (healthy) food messages are relayed and how they are understood. The observation guide will consist of: How does the classroom environment support learning? Appropriate facilities for cooking, space to move around the classroom, lighting, warmth etc) ; How do students respond to the information provided (number of interactions with teacher, note taking,

engagement) ; What are the teaching outcomes for the session (taken from curriculum).

Data Analyses:

Will vary depending on the method being employed - all data will be qualitative. A reflexive approach will be adopted by the researchers (Denscombe, 2010) engaging in delivery of the project, which will permit ongoing thematic analyses to be iteratively carried out. Similarly, using 'Constant comparative analysis' (Hewitt-Taylor 2001), which analyses multiple methods concurrently, focus group transcripts can be coded, then categories and themes developed and interpreted by the research team members. Analysis will be on going, using qualitative data packages, such as Nvivo10 (2011). Analyses aim to be as faithful as possible to any respondents' accounts. In terms of triangulation, all observations and field notes will be kept as these are recommended, particularly for non-verbal communications (Fade, 2004). The research team will be reflexive in understanding their role in interpreting findings and they will endeavour to act in a way so as not to exaggerate any potential power imbalance (Liamputtong, 2007).

Anticipated findings and their relevance

Anticipated findings and their relevance

This Schools project will be used to inform the FoodSEqual Plymouth project and national consortium project. It will focus on working closely with disadvantaged communities, particularly young people who are often forgotten voices in this arena, to jointly imagine new solutions to address a lack of access to healthy, sustainable food. The schools project will permit the voices of young people to inform our wider project objectives around uniting researchers and food industry representatives with charity leaders to reimagine how food policy, products and supply chains can be co-developed.

FoodSEqual will use innovative (bottom-up) 'co-production' approaches, effectively putting communities at the heart of the work by setting up an active 'Community Food Researcher' team in Plymouth which will support the research processes and data collection. If any of the school pupils are interested in the wider project, we have opportunities for further involvement (with permission from gatekeeper and parents of course).

Ethical aspects of research

Please indicate how you will ensure this research conforms to each clause of the University of Plymouth's [Principles for Research Involving Human Participants](#). Please address each of the ethical principles set out below

Informed consent

Consent will firstly be secured by gatekeeper (school) using tailored participant information sheet and consent form (see appendices B and C) so that access to sample can then be supported. Further consent will be secured via parents using the schools permissions processes already in place.

To protect the welfare of research participants the nature of the study is clearly explained via an information sheet and flyer (Appendix E and F). In keeping with best practice the researchers will also endeavour to explain the study in person (National Research Ethics Service (NRES), 2011). If a participant cannot read, the information sheet can be read out like a script (NRES, 2011). Informed written consent will be sought from parents of all participants via the schools permissions processes (see appendix G for permissions sheet/consent form). On the day of the focus groups, the research purpose will also be explained to the children for assent purposes (National Academies Press, 2004), and the research team will consolidate ethical aspects (around voluntary nature of their participation and right to withdraw).

The Gatekeepers organisation (school) who have already provided consent, may also need to be present for communication purposes where necessary.

Equality and diversity

We already have verbal agreement from the school (gatekeeper) to run our curriculum enrichment project. This school has a diverse pupil community, consisting of many lower income families so is representative of vulnerable and disadvantaged communities. Our sample will draw from families within the Whitleigh community. Parents may be unemployed, have disabilities, and form part of other minority groups who are particularly at risk of food insecurity.

At the heart of the FoodSEqual project is the belief that a right to food is the right to dignity. We deeply acknowledge the need for non-judgement, sensitivity & inclusion when working with often vulnerable disadvantaged communities to combat stigma. Our ethos is to offer

inclusive, holistic, safe (fun/creative) food research activities for the children (and their parents) to engage with. We will support participants with incentives for engagement to include any travel/time reimbursement. We feel this is vital to support our community groups. We will only request relevant (GDPR compliant) personal data from participants that falls within the equality and diversity agenda.

Openness and honesty

It will be important to make it clear to any participants in the study that anything they say will be confidential and will not affect future care or support they receive. Participants will be informed before taking part in the study that if they divulge information during any of the participatory methods that is demonstrating harm to others confidentiality may need to be breached. We will share preliminary data with the pupils as it emerges from the analyses.

Deception

Not being used

Right to withdraw

Participation will be voluntary, and individuals will be informed of their right to withdraw at any point during the study, without reprisal. Should participants choose to withdraw during the study, we will endeavour to remove their data from analysis, although there may be occasion where this is not possible. For example, if they withdraw from a focus group or other recorded group activity after the data collection has started, the data collected up to that point will be retained. This is because, as it is a group discussion, the sense of the data will be lost. None of that participant's words will be used in the reporting of the data.

Protection from harm

Children/young people; vulnerable adults; sensitive topics; permission of parent and gatekeeper

Vulnerability - It may be that some participants find it distressing talking about their food experiences. The researchers will be mindful of this and will ensure that if participants do become distressed, they can be referred on for appropriate support. The focus group(s) or other creative research activity will also be terminated if necessary. All focus groups will take place in an appropriately safe environment for the participants needs, and where necessary lone working policies will be followed. The school and relevant teachers (and volunteers) will be informed of participants involvement as a routine precaution.

The researchers acknowledge that working with children and potentially vulnerable parents (from disadvantaged communities) will present certain challenges such as requirement for empathy and diplomacy around sensitive topics within the remit of the research. Our

research team already have direct practitioner experience working with vulnerable groups. The team will, nonetheless, be actively involved in regular communications with the various gatekeepers and their support teams, who have a wealth of experience on the sensitivities involved in working within this area.

Debrief

As participants will be made fully aware of the purpose of the research there is no formal requirement for debriefing, however in the true nature of co-production methodologies, the research team will endeavour to include ongoing debriefing throughout the various stages of the school project. Our consultant researcher (JG) will offer support and de-brief sessions at each of the four taster days – so she will become the consistent familiar face for the pupils to engage with along the project timeline (see appendix A). The researcher will ask participants at the end of the focus group(s) if they have any worries about what has been said and check that they are feeling alright before they leave. Appropriate support and advice will be offered (via school channels) if necessary.

Dissemination

Participants are informed and will give consent that their data can be used for dissemination purpose, eg reports, publications and conferences presentations. Also possible use of any creative outputs generated during curriculum enrichment events (eg. photographs, collage, film) for exhibitions and other participatory events, with consent being sought for this.

Anonymity

Data will not be reported specifically at the individual level, so anonymity will be maintained. Some creative methods (eg photographs) may have potential to reveal identities.

Participants (parents) will be given the option of giving consent for all, some or none of their creative outputs to be used in dissemination. It is possible that individuals may not remain anonymous if they consent to allowing photographs/outputs to be published. The researcher will discuss with parents the possible implications of this during the taster sessions. It is envisaged that an exhibition of photographs and other creative outputs may form part of the dissemination. All participants will be consulted about confidentiality/anonymity regarding any public exhibition of photographs/other creative outputs

Confidentiality

All participants' personal details will remain confidential and anonymous - with pseudonyms being used during write-ups or other dissemination. No one apart from the research team will have access to the consent forms. This will be the only documentation to contain the names of the participants. No one apart from the research team will have access to the

data/consent forms. Any observational notes, photos and documents will be coded and stored systematically in an electronic password protected format using a PC/laptop (GDPR compliant). Audio files and transcripts will be anonymised and will be stored electronically in the same manner as outlined above (any hard copies will be destroyed to ensure that confidentiality is not breached).

Participants will be informed that all data will be kept for a minimum of 10 years. Data on any computer used for transcribing and analysis will be stored in a password-secured and encrypted folder and access restricted to the research team. The audio files will be destroyed at the end of the study and all data including transcripts will be stored for a minimum of 10 years (as per Plymouth University policy). The study will comply with the Data Protection Act (Great Britain. GDPR Protection Act 2018).

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